

Magnetic Properties of $\text{Pb}_6\text{Co}_9(\text{TeO}_6)_5$ single crystal

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$\text{Pb}_6\text{Co}_9(\text{TeO}_6)_5$ has a unique type of magnetic spin lattice structure, where the spin lattice consists of four different Co ions sites with distorted octahedral coordination. DC magnetization measurements exhibits, a complex magnetic behavior, ferromagnetic transition (T_C) at ~ 21.5 K. At lower magnetic fields, ZFC (Zero-field-cooled) and FC (field-cooled) curves show a broad hump at $T_b \sim 10.8$ K and a shoulder peak at $T_s \sim 6.2$ K below T_C , which are suppressed in higher applied magnetic fields. AC susceptibility and specific heat (CP) measurements also confirm the FM transition at low-temperature, however, there is no trace of peak observed except T_C . Remarkably, the negative Curie-Weiss constant reveals in $H \parallel c$, $H \perp c$ and powder sample at high temperatures, suggesting antiferromagnetic (AFM) interactions at high temperatures. The frustration factor, is found to be 7.2 along $H \parallel c$ while almost absent in $H \perp c$ and also reduced with applying higher magnetic fields. The large coercive curve (HC) observed (1.3 T) at 2 K applying magnetic field along $H \parallel c$, whereas linear magnetization curve exhibits for $H \perp c$. These behaviors indicate the highly anisotropy nature of present compound. The short-range magnetic spin correlation is present above T_C .